

RUSSIA-UKRAINE CONFLICT: THE FAÇADE OF CIVILISATIONISM OF RUSSIA AS AN ALIBI FOR THE WAR

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Abstract

The Russian invasion of Ukraine on 24 February 2022 has again sparked a major debate in the international academic and foreign policy circles about the evolving overall dynamics of geopolitics in Europe, including Russian geopolitics, and perturbed researchers to have a fresh look at the aggressive attitude of Russia towards the West particularly USA and vice versa. The paper argues that the majority of the Ukrainians have rejected the whole manufactured narrative of Civilisationism in the post-Soviet space by Russia to re-capture the territories within its so-called sphere of privileged interests. Various semantic tools, like civilizational security, identity, and Russia's self-proclaimed Civilizational State, contradict the aspirations of building a modern political Ukrainian nation. In this broader context, the paper will explore the underlying causes, some historical, some new, which lead to the contemporary Russia-Ukraine conflict while debunking the juggernaut of Huntingtonian clash of civilizations per se. The article offers a perspective on how Russia forced alternative identities instead by launching attacks on Ukraine, Georgia, and Crimea while also using soft and sharp power tactics like unleashing a barrage of propaganda and an information war through media and academia while denying Ukraine its distinctive national identity after the consolidation of the Ukrainian national identity in the post-Orange Revolution and Euro Maidan protests. The paper dismisses the conflict as a civilizational one, as framed by Putin, and substantiates the argument by showing that strategic projects like Russkiy Mir and Novorossia have not achieved substantial gains in the foreign policy of Russia. The paper shows that studying the balance of power and the change in European security architecture can better explain the tragic nature of conflict and save the potential abuse of the civilizational construct. The present study employs

a descriptive and qualitative technique to examine the role of Russian civilizational propaganda in the conflict and the current war.

Keywords: *Russian Civilization; civilizational identity; civilizational State; modern political Ukrainian nation; façade of Civilisationism.*

Introduction

The terminology surrounding the Ukraine conflict has been very carefully framed (distorted) by the leaders of the major countries party to it and popularized to such an extent with the support of the media, academia, and whole propaganda machinery that it becomes next to impossible to separate the wheat from the chaff. The paper substantiates the argument with the help of vast academic arguments on both sides of the conflict that the conflict in Eastern Europe and the wars of 2014 and 2022 over Ukraine resulted not because of a Clash of Civilizations but as a result of Clash of geopolitical interests, the mismanagement of European Security architecture, imbalance in Balance of Power and antagonistic perspectives of world order. The paper essentially claims that the main reason for the current crisis is not cultural and religious ties or differences but rather a clear clash over the settlement of national interests between the West and Russia because “Ukraine’s foreign policy towards international relations threatens Russia’s hegemony and political and economic interest” (Sharif et al., 2023). But at the same time, the critique of the narrative of civilizational belonging needs to be carefully contextualized and examined.

The paper does not consider this European conflict as a civilizational one; instead, it argues that the nation-states -inherently problematic per se are the primary and viable forces on the world stage and will remain so for the future. Authors assume that by disguising its underlying geopolitical goals and hunger for power, Russia’s rhetorical usage of cultural and civilizational semantics, act as a cover or justification for its military actions in Ukraine. This ostensible civilizational division of the world along cultural and civilizational lines, acts as a mask, a kind of noble lie, a hoax promoted by Russian regime particularly Putin to hide his aggressive foreign policy choices. Civilisationism is a strategic tool employed to hide the neo-imperialistic tendencies of the Russian civilizational state. The civilizational State and its security have become handy tools in the hands of populist and authoritarian leaders to legitimize their manifestations of hunger for power. Despite its inherent flaws, the

conflictual mapping of East Europe and other regions plays a significant role in shaping public opinion, politics, and nation-state relations. It also influences mutual perceptions, which would not have influenced the interactions between sovereign states in a rational world. Therefore, assuming the Russian Civilisationism as a facade, the paper will analyze the present crisis and the larger conflict without diving into much detail about the merits, criticisms, and flaws of civilizational debate already undertaken to exhaustion by the scholars.

The paper argues that the conflict and the consequent war can neither be theoretically (justly) placed within the same Civilization (Orthodox Russia and Orthodox Ukraine) nor between two competing civilizations (Orthodox Russia and Liberal Christian USA) as Huntington, Russia, particularly Putin and the leadership of USA want us to believe. The rhetorical lies of the politicians and their careful crafting of the conflict along the civilizational lines ostensibly provide them a cloak to hide the real goals of their (immoral) tactics. Therefore, the main objective of the article is to deconstruct the nature of aggressive civilizational claims of the Russian state particularly Putin's over the independent state of Ukraine. Though there are visible cultural similarities and civilizational linkages, but that does not give Putin a green flag to violate the International laws and territorial sovereignty of another state. In his context, the article tries to locate the problem within the Civilizational paradigm itself, while also debunking the narrative of Russian Civilizational Project. While the article clearly, at length identifies the causes of the war and the weakness of the Russian Civilizational project, it argues that the civilizational narrative of Russia is a façade instead of being real and the only cause of the larger crisis, leading to the present war. Therefore, the real causes of the conflict need to be explored, and the façade of Civilisationism as an alibi for the war over Ukraine, needs to be deconstructed.

Methodology

Keeping under consideration the nature and objectives of the research paper, a Descriptive Qualitative research methodology has been used to review the relevant literature and analyze the same. The secondary sources of data collection such as published research papers, related books, journal articles, websites, surveys and media broadcasts have been used. Also the methodology used in this paper is archival and open sourced including the

official state documents, political leader's speeches and public statements in the press media were analyzed and interpreted. Two compatible research methods used sequentially to analyze the collected Secondary Qualitative literature are Content analysis, and Thematic analysis. Content analysis, which is exploratory and analytical in character, is the main research approach employed. It entails methodically examining media and document material to find themes, patterns, and meanings which takes us to the next step of identifying and locating the recurring themes of our research paper through thematic analysis. The structure of the study entails four major themes. The first theme sets the context of the study by discussing the conceptual category of civilisations and provides a brief review of the literature. The second theme analyses the (real) causes responsible for this conflict which are identified in the major academic studies as the problem in the balance of power and contemporary European security architecture. The third theme discusses the ostensible framing of the conflict along the civilizational lines which gives Russia an edge to manipulate the world opinion in its favor and overshadow its aggressive behaviour towards Ukraine. The conceptual category of civilisational division of the world is examined and negated through highlighting the inherent flaws and autocratic tendencies of such division. It's argued that nation-state, although flawed, are still a viable source of loyalty to the citizens and can act as a bulwark against the civilisational state concept in general and Russian civilisational adventurism in particular. The fourth theme dismisses the conflict as a civilisational one as framed by Putin and substantiates the argument by showing that the strategic projects like *Ruskiy mir* and *Novorossia* have not achieved substantial gains in the foreign policy of Russia. The fourth and final theme makes a case for upholding a sovereign Ukrainian state and respect for Ukrainian identity as a rebuttal to the Russian neo-imperialist Civilisational state. Overall the present study employs a descriptive and qualitative technique to examine the role of Russian civilisational propaganda in the conflict and the current war.

Civilization: A Conceptual Framework

From a philosophical and political science perspective, the idea of civilisation is not new. Nonetheless, politicians and academics have mostly disregarded it for the better part of the 20th century, despite the appearance of a few very intellectually significant classical works that treated civilisation as a unit of historical and political analysis. The

description of Western civilisation by Oswald Spengler is a work of immense intellectual significance and a crucial methodological manual for the study of civilisations in general (Spengler, 1918). In addition to providing a rigorous analytical examination of the origins and interrelationships of preexisting and extant civilisations, Arnold Toynbee's "Study of History" offers a comprehensive historical narrative of their development and demise (Toynbee, 1946). From a social-psychological perspective, Carl Jung develops the idea of civilisational analysis further. He gives us his concept of the "collective unconscious" from 1912, which serves as the foundation for common civilisational outlooks, perceptions, and customs. From 1933 onward, he refined and expanded upon this concept, culminating it in the 1959 book *The Archetypes and the Collective Unconscious* (Jung, 1959). By examining the links between civilisations and their potential for cultural, economic, and military confrontation, Samuel Huntington, who was influenced by Toynbee's work, elevated the concept of civilisation to the level of international politics in his landmark work *Clash of Civilisations* (Huntington, 1996 a). *World Order* by Henry Kissinger provides a perceptive historical account of how international politics have changed over the previous ten centuries (Kissinger, 2014 b).

Yet, Civilisations have not been problematized widely in International Relations. For Wallerstein civilisation is a 'particular concatenation of worldview, customs, structures, and culture (both material and high culture) which forms some kind of historical whole and which coexists (if not always simultaneously) with other varieties of this phenomenon' (Wallerstein, 1992, p. 215). Toynbee argues that civilisational forces in action 'are not national' but proceed 'from wider causes, which operate upon each of the parts and are not intelligible in their partial orientation unless a comprehensive view is taken of their operation throughout the society' (Toynbee, 1946, p. 3). A civilisation is frequently comprised of several countries and is not limited to just one. A civilisation, or one of several, may comprise numerous states, much as the global human civilization may comprise numerous civilisations. A significant consequence of this state of affairs is that civilisational boundaries are ill-defined and can cross specific states, separating them into segments and leaving such nations vulnerable to internal strife or collapse (Dugin, 2012, p. 106–7; Huntington, 1996a, p. 37). On the other side, civilisations are "mortal" and do not fit into neat classifications (Huntington, 1996a, p. 43).

Yet, Civilisations are very long lived and reflect the "realities of the extreme *longue duree*," (Braudel and Mayne, 1993, p. 209–10), notwithstanding their impending death. In their constant evolution and adaptation, civilizations outlast and endure nations, empires, governments, and even ideologies.

Of the two notions of civilisation, ‘a civilisation’ is undoubtedly the more contentious and ambiguous. This is due to the fact that ‘the civilisation’ refers to mankind in all of its forms, making it both semantically inclusive and open. But the definition of ‘a civilisation’ is more limited and encompasses a wide range of identity-related statements that are intricate, contentious, ideological, and filled with values and liable to cause rifts in academia or even politics. The very identities produced or reproduced at the national level by an institutionalized state system are “thick identities”, instead of “thinner identities” (Terlouw, 2016, p. 45-46) generated at the civilisational levels, as becoming one of them is more elusive and does not always entail instantaneous citizen-like responsibilities and duties. Either way, civilisational identities are best understood as multi-layered networks made up of elements such as politics, technology, religion, economics, and culture that combine to create a complex but recognizable web. The identities of civilisations are not fixed nor easily imposed on individuals if their own aspirations and desires lead them in a different direction. Civilisation is based on people's belief that they are part of a certain historical current that is shaped by culturally motivated, sometimes irrational justifications. A rooted feeling of belonging is the foundation for a civilisation's members to anchor their sense of purpose, even while the ultimate historical destination is uncertain. This succinct understanding of the genesis of the civilisation provides a conceptual framework while dealing with the civilisational angle of the broader (Russia-West and Russia-Ukraine) conflict.

The real cause(s) of conflict: problems with the balance of power and European security architecture

The diversity and disagreements in the vast scholarship of international politics in tracing the root causes of the Russia- Ukraine conflict or the fractured Russia-US relationship becomes obvious from a cursory look at the relevant literature. Added to this academic contestation is the Statist propaganda to keep one's image clean while framing another side as an evil, dark force waiting to overturn the Order (global here) and overrun

the forces of good. It becomes a herculean task to come up with an objective analysis of the conflict, but at the same time, it becomes a matter of academic responsibility and integrity. So are the causes of conflict embedded in Russia's imperialist designs and its nostalgia for the lost supremacy in the pre-Soviet space, which it wants to reclaim back by taking over the Ukrainian State? Or is it the geopolitical and economic imperative that Russia wants to take advantage of? Is it the US and the NATO expansion into the Russian (pre-Cold War Soviet space) sphere of privileged interests that Putin claims is an exclusive area of the Russian State? Or is there an Orthodox Christian Civilizational State whose fate and survival are entrusted to Russia, now Putin's, or is this civilizational guise a bluff to control the resource-rich geopolitical and geostrategic space? Is it all of these, or is it none of these?

Scholars and foreign policy analysts at one end of the spectrum argue that "Russia pursues aggressive policies in the post-Soviet space, harbors expansionist ambitions, and is the main culprit of the Ukraine crisis. At the other end are those who say that Moscow's policies are mainly defensive and aim to protect Russia against aggressive encroachments from Western powers, whose reckless actions led to the crisis over Ukraine" (Götz, 2018, p. 251). The division is visible while considering the causes and behavior responsible for the Ukraine Crisis⁵. The West and its supporters see "the crisis in Ukraine sparked by Russian intervention in the internal affairs of Ukraine via the illegal annexation of Crimea and the backing of separatist groups in the Donbas region" (Wolff, 2015, p. 1103). For Russia and its allies "origins of the Ukraine crisis lie in NATO's decision to expand the alliance eastward. The Russian government views the situation in Ukraine through a lens of repeated Western betrayal, creeping NATO encroachment, and disrespect for its security concern" (Wolff, 2015, p. 1103). These official positions have also divided academia, where arguments and counterarguments are advanced on both sides of the spectrum to justify their respective positions. Russia justified its saber-rattle and annexation on the pretext of Ukraine joining NATO, the dominance of Neo-Nazi forces in Ukrainian politics, and the suppression of the Russian language and culture in Ukrainian society. Both narratives have to be balanced to make a proper sense of this protracted conflict. Falling for one narrative and completely absolving the other side has worsened the situation, as D'Anieri argues there are unbridgeable enduring differences (D'Anieri, 2019). He points

out three main factors, "the security dilemma, the impact of democratization on geopolitics, and the incompatible goals of a post-Cold War Europe" (D'Anieri 2019, p. i), that have created much trouble for the peaceful way out of this conflict.

In a recent paper, Mearsheimer made two main observations regarding the continuing war and the root cause of the conflict in Eurasia:

"First, the United States is principally responsible for causing the Ukraine crisis. This is not to deny that Putin started the war and that he is responsible for Russia's conduct on the battlefield. Nor is it to deny that America's allies bear some responsibility...the United States has pushed forward policies toward Ukraine that Putin and his colleagues see as an existential threat to their country. Second, the Biden administration has reacted to the outbreak of the war by doubling down against Russia. Washington and its Western allies are committed to decisively defeating Russia in Ukraine and employing comprehensive sanctions to greatly weaken Russian power" (Mearsheimer, 2022, p. 12).

This line of thinking resonates within the larger academic circles and gives a closer picture of the conflictual dynamics of East Europe. Similarly, for Wayne Merr, Russia and the EU share the burden of the conflict, but "it was Moscow's decision to militarize the competition that fundamentally altered the character and consequences of the conflict" (Merry, 2016, p. 27).

The 2008 NATO summit in Bucharest was a watershed moment when the alliance announced the inclusion of Georgia and Ukraine in its fold, provoking strong opposition from the Russian side. "Seen in this light, the proximate cause for the Ukrainian conflict– the clash between the EU's Eastern Partnership Policy and Russia's Eurasian Union – is a symptom of the broader geopolitical dynamics that emerged under Uni-polarity" (Barkanov, 2015, p. 211) and continues to shape the events even in the aftermath of Uni-polarity.

Therefore, the roots of this geopolitical crisis lie in the fractured structural-institutional system of the post-Cold War era. Rather than being an individual problem (without being oblivious to the role of individual personalities), it is a deep and wider problem of European security order per se. "A systemic level account highlighting the significance of the balance of power in precipitating the Ukrainian crisis is important because it situates the conflict in a broader political and historical context"

(Barkanov, 2015, p. 211). It gives a perspective to picture the crisis as a response by the Russian State and China to the US and NATO expansion and the West's expansion tactics to alleviate its security fears against these rising powers. "NATO enlargement creates a security dilemma: every addition to NATO's membership inherently detracts from Russian security and causes Russia to react by seeking greater security" (Wolff, 2015, p. 1111). This phenomenon acts both ways, as each side views the other's security built-up aimed against the rise in its capabilities of power. This fear of vulnerability through security anxiety directly affects the (im) balance of power between the two sides. To look after Russia's (same for China as well) "perceived threat, Russia's national security establishment has long emphasized the importance of possessing strategic depth and buffer zones" (Götz & Staun, 2022, p. 482). Russia considers itself entitled to be a major power in Eastern Europe, aspiring to go back to the historic Soviet supremacy. Moscow's great power vision "to have a sphere of influence in its Eurasian neighborhood" (Götz & Staun, 2022, p. 482) is challenged by Kyiv fostering closer relationships with Washington and NATO. Russia's annexation of Crimea (2014) and the war of aggression over Georgia (2008), and Ukraine (2014; 2022) is the logical systemic (side) effect of such a structural change in the international political arena.

The Russian civilizational façade

The civilizational mapping of the world's conflicts and debates has been around for many decades, competing as an alternative with some already established theories. Even though some scholars have called to kill Civilization as a concept (Jennings, 2016, p. 7), others, because of the complexity of the concept, have argued for not referring to it at all (Appiah, 2016, p. 9), "contemporary politics and recent academic literature, however, increasingly deploy Civilization as a frame of reference in international exchange (Chebankova, 2021, p. 19). This leads to the "emergence of the civilizational model of international dialogue" (Chebankova & Dutkiewicz, 2021, p. 159).

However, the concept of a Civilizational-State, recently in vogue among Russian policy circles, is not a natural or a logical historical inevitable step as it is projected both inside Russia and to the outside world. Rather, its usage has been instrumental and functional for the Russian Civilizational project. This project is driven by the historical narratives of the past, carefully constructed to justify the creation of a (Russian) civilizational

entity. Putin, as he is shaped by history like everybody else, has used the same history for his purposes and has summoned up the spirits of the past to present the current crisis in his own desired expedient way (Mctague, 2022).

In a later book, “Who Are We? The Challenges to America’s National Identity” published in 2004, Huntington makes an argument in favor of consolidating the national identity of America and laments that its “national identity has been eroded by the problems of assimilating massive numbers of primarily Hispanic immigrants, bilingualism, multiculturalism, the devaluation of citizenship, and the ‘denationalization’ of American elites” (Huntington, 2004b, p. 405). For him the American national identity and nation is at the receiving end and makes a clarion call to “reassert the core values that make us Americans” (Huntington, 2004b, p. 405). Juxtaposing this argument against his earlier argument of Civilizational clash makes his claims hollow and contradictory. Mathematically, it is like multiplying any given number set with zero. Suppose one accepts his propagation of unique American national identity. In that case, he assumes nation-states as the primary, supreme, and viable forces of shaping identity politics. This cancels his earlier argumentation of the supremacy of civilizational dominance in international politics as an alternative to nation-states and national identity. If one accepts one of his two arguments, then the other argument falls apart, a typical behavioral cognitive dissonance tendency, so to say. Therefore, critics of the Huntingtonian Civilizational paradigm challenge it for pushing the State to a secondary role in the international system. They argue that the significance of nation-states cannot be belittled as the dawn has only started for this new phenomenon. “The primary cultural unit in international politics remains the nation—ethnic, tribal, religious, or political- not the civilization” (Rubenstein & Crocker, 1994, p. 113).

Further, two major discrepancies emerge from the civilizational modeling of world politics. First, failure to accept that “ethnic nations may be as resistant to incorporation in multinational civilizational blocs as they were to absorption by colonialist empires. Second, in order to reassert the importance of cultural factors in international politics, he turns liberal and Marxist reductionism on its head, arguing that cultural differences have become the primary facilitator of international conflict rather than one basis (among others) for conflict mobilization” (Rubenstein & Crocker,

1994, p. 121). The civilizational states' covert modus operandi to subsume the nation-states within its larger cultural family is not to give them membership in a powerful and flourishing society or to fulfill some great ecclesiastical command but to win the zero-sum game of struggle for global power. For this to happen, the reproduction of thick identities at the nation-state level has to be replaced or overcome by the thin identities of the Civilizational rallying, but “belonging to them is more elusive and does not have to generate immediate citizen-like obligations” (Coker, 2019, p. 11). It bestows nation-states the highest degree of political loyalty commanded by its citizens. It subsumes narrower allegiances, which become part of the nation-state's loyalty. Linguistic or religious communities, civilizations, and other groups that transcend national boundaries have historically demanded less fervent allegiance and devotion (Fukuyama, 1996). Therefore, coercive means are used to keep an ethnic nation(s) within the larger civilizational family or to make a separate ethnic nation accept this family as its destiny is based solely on power politics and the national interests of powerful states. Ukraine has become a trophy, a prize to be won after the contestations between the West versus Russia and Russia against Ukraine over this very rich mineral and agricultural land is over.

For all the credit and explanatory value that Huntington's Clash of Civilizations narrative deserves and the fervor his thesis created among his admirers and critics, this novel conceptual construction at the base of it has a chauvinistic imperialistic rationale. It gives powerful big countries free rein to establish their control over weaker ones and make them their vestiges in the name of arbitrary civilizational ties. Putin, Xi, and others who tread upon an imaginary path of civilizational historicism have used these narratives to justify their authoritarian proclivities, and the recent successful popularity of the right wing populists in both the West and Europe is something to be kept eye on (Haynes, 2019). “Trump's former chief ideologist, Steve Bannon, openly sympathized with Putin's civilizational agenda, saying that, similarly, the Judeo-Christian West was at risk, too” (Hirsh, 2022, p. 10) while Trump praised the war on Ukraine initially as an act of genius, from which he later retreated after harsh criticism. Hungarian Premier Victor Orban considered a close friend of Putin, defeated the national opposition parties who had called for Hungary to support Ukraine. In France, the opposition party presidential candidate Marine Le Pen (who wants closer ties with Russia) is becoming famous

ahead of the 18 August 2024 scheduled elections, while Serbia's pro-Russia president, Aleksandar Vucic, has already won. First Soviet Communism, now this Russian propaganda of alternative civilizational modernity, presents an alternative to the West from a spiritual and cultural side and redeems its long cherished aspirations for pre-soviet great power status. The ostensible Civilizational identity based upon the so-called civilizational consciousness of the orthodox Christian people, which Russia is trying to manufacture, nonetheless, is (unfortunately) getting increasing support from the rising number of states. Mearsheimer made an interesting observation against such a Russian civilizational notion and its supporters in a recent 2022 article where he wrote, "Putin was not interested in making Ukraine a part of Russia; he was interested in making sure it did not become a springboard for Western aggression against Russia" (Mearsheimer, 2022, p. 15).

Even if we accept the central defining logic of the thesis that the "conflict between groups in different civilizations will be more frequent, more sustained and more violent than conflicts between groups in the same civilization" (Aroua, 2006, p. 1), then the conflicts within the same civilizations turn the whole narrative topsy-turvy. The civilizational paradigm gives civilizational identities, encompassing culture and cultural identities, the highest role in influencing how societies in the post-Cold War era integrate, break up, and engage in conflict (Evans & Huntington, 1997, p. 691). Ideological contestations will then take a back seat while differences in civilizational identities will bloom, shaping the wars and conflicts in the post-Cold War setup. However, "the conflicts in Georgia (2008) and Ukraine (2014; 2022) have pitted people of the same Russian (Orthodox) civilization against one another", showing a major fault in the civilizational narrative (Hovorun, 2016, p. 163). Among the nine major civilizations in which Huntington divides the globe, the intra-civilizational fractures, civil wars, and conflicts have nullified the "self-fulfilling prophesy" (Assumpcao, 2020). The conflict in the Middle East (Israel-Palestine), South Asia (India-Pakistan-Bangladesh), Eastern Asia (China-Taiwan), and Africa involve clear examples of the backlash against Civilizations and Civilizational State and the powerful assertion of the so-called nation-state⁶. Paul Weller notes "the essentialising and bloc approach to cultures and societies, arguing that such an approach does not take sufficient account of the differences and sometimes fault-lines and conflicts within societies and cultural groups" (Weller, 2010, p. 83).

The invasion of a civilizational kin by a larger state with civilizational linkages reflects the trouble within the civilizational perspective itself. A powerful state claiming to be the torchbearer of a unique civilization with some common identifiable similarities with a small state has no moral authority to override the national sovereignty and its national aspirations based on these common cultural similarities. According to this civilizational narrative, it allows the smaller, less powerful states to take advantage of a powerful security umbrella known as civilizational security. "Civilizational security refers to a country's security stemming from belonging to a cultural zone or a civilization" (Lewicki, 2023, p. 11). The benefits of joining one's ancestral home and civilizational kin should be the major driver of bringing the civilizational states into a larger state-civilization model. However, such rallying around the civilizational flag has been a missing phenomenon in contemporary international politics. Ukraine has been a primary example of such a negative development for a successful future Civilizational debate. Taiwan has also given a sharp debacle to the Chinese narratives of forming a Confucian Sinic Civilization. Conflicts, wars, and civil unrest between and among the Muslim states have laid bare the un-successful claims of forming 'Ummah' on these very civilizational lines. Russia believes it has a deep historical and cultural relationship with Ukraine, something Putin and his coterie have long highlighted (Götz, 2018) and the restoration of Novorossiya (New Russia; Tsarist term for predominantly Ukraine's Russian-speaking entire south-east). Relentlessly endorsing the civilizational decision to live in *Russkiy mir* (the Russian World) as opposed to Europe, Putin has called Russians and Ukrainians *Odin Narod* (one people). Thus, Tatiana Zhurzhenko argues that Ukraine is considered to be part of a thousand-year-old Russian Orthodox civilization with ties far deeper than any recent 'artificial' construction of national identity (Zhurzhenko, 2014, p. 249-267).

Under the leadership of Russia, with Putin as its savior, the Orthodox Christian Civilizational-State is proposed as a penance for all the ills against the expanding Western Civilization. Here, (Russian) Civilizations, in the broadest sense, are "presented as internally coherent entities equipped with the state-like capacity to act, whereas in reality, civilizations are ever-changing, incoherent, and complex"(Katzenstein, 2010, p. 11-25). Nevertheless, this civilizational state concept, now popularized as the *Russkiy Mir*, is invoked by the leadership of the

Russian State as a means by which a certain regime can support its authority and influence political outcomes to suit its objectives (Coker, 2019).

Russkiy Mir: A success story or a failed foreign policy tool

Following Putin's Munich Speech (2007) and Georgian conflict (2008), the foreign policy of Russia was radically reshaped in-line with the arguments of Eurasianism and according to the whims of Putin. To advance Russian language and culture both locally and globally, Putin signed an order in June 2007 establishing the Russkiy Mir Foundation. Russkiy mir is typically used to describe a transnational group of people bound together by a common heritage and set of values, by the Russian language and culture, by Orthodox religious beliefs, and by their allegiance to the Russian state (which refers to both the USSR and the Russian Empire). As a soft power tool of Russia and Putin Russkiy Mir is "strongly associated with discourses of a shared past and with the common values, culture and history that arise from it" (Bohomolov & Lytvynenko, 2012, p. 3).

It was first used in Russian political discourse in the late 1990s, in the wake of the USSR's disintegration and the nation's ensuing search for a national identity. It was based on the principle that Russia had a moral obligation to protect the rights, language, and culture of all Russian speakers worldwide, especially those in the erstwhile Soviet Union. A related proclamation on the "Concept of Humanitarian Policy of the Russian Federation Abroad" (Bergmann, 2022) was signed by Vladimir Putin on September 5, 2022. Kremlin argues that the lengthy (more than thirty pages) paper is an indispensable component of Russia's foreign policy strategy and national security plan. Through this document what Putin wants to achieve is to reinvigorate the notion of Russianness and instill a new life in the Russkiy mir project.

An ideological rationale for Russian intervention in the near abroad that the Kremlin may use to deflect criticism from across the world is provided by the rhetorical building of a socially and linguistically homogeneous Russkiy Mir spread across the Eastern Europe. This idea that the Russian civilization is fragmented and divided by artificial post-cold war borders is reflected behind the logic of constructing a pan- Russian geopolitical space through Russkiy mir. In addition to serving as a major catalyst for

Putin's annexation of Crimea in 2014, the notion of building a Russkiy Mir is also serving as a rationale for Putin's invasion of Ukraine in 2022 (Young, 2022). Russkiy Mir has become a central defining logic of Putin's Strategic thought (Cotter, 2016) which advocates for protecting the Russian speaking people 'compatriots' across the borders (Pieper, 2020). "Adding a cultural dimension to this conflict is also intended to help mobilize the Russian public and stoke nationalism against the West in support of a costly and possibly ruinous war in Ukraine" (Bergmann, 2022).

"What is ultimately so striking about Putin's gamble is that, in the end, the geopolitical world order it will help to create is almost exactly the opposite of the one he sought to avoid by invading Ukraine in the first place: a diminution of the Russkiy Mir" (Gioe & Styles, 2022, p. 598). Certainly, with all the state power behind the project, it has not materialized as a great success story of Russia. There are varied reasons for its failure or limited success as some western scholars argue, as the policy did not export well and could not connect with the wider diaspora and the so called core of Orthodox Civilization particularly the two Slavic nations- Ukraine, and Belarus.

At the core of Russkiy Mir is the assumption of cultural homogeneity of the Slavic nations who are to be protected (from west) and united under the broader Russian Civilizational umbrella. Although there are cultural as well as linguistic similarities among Russia and its surrounding nations, but it does not take into account the diverse cultural identities and divisions which also exist in reality. This division along the cultural (fault) lines makes it impossible to assert a singular Russian identity across the nations. Subsuming the other alternative (national) identities under the singular Russian identity and patronizing the Russian identity while suppressing or belittling other identities acts as a bulwark against the political unison of the so called Eurasia. Because of these fears, Russkiy Mir is negatively perceived as a geopolitical tool to control and influence the foreign policies of neighboring states. The Crimean war (2008) and the Ukraine war (2014, 2022) can also be seen as the efforts of these governments to mount some resistance to such revanchist ideas. Even people of the same Russian ethnic origin and having common cultural ties with Russia, living in other nations, does not necessarily mean that they cherish the same perspectives and political allegiances as the Russian citizens do. This unity in diversity styled project is made more difficult to

achieve by the geo-political context in which it operates where the Russian regime has tried to control the territories forcefully, through war. No state and people are going to shower petals on an aggressor, no nation wants another nation to colonize it, especially when the children and unarmed are killed on the streets. This limited success of Russkiy Mir in the foreign policy of Russia can be attributed to the authoritarian governance style of Putin and also the continuous catch of the Western values of liberalism and freedom.

Ukraine for Ukrainians'

The hard truth about international politics is that the powerful states dominate the world's political affairs, as the famous Melian dialogue wisdom retells, do what they have the power to do and the weaker states accept what they have to accept. Although strategically important and resourceful, Contemporary Africa, Latin America, the Middle East, etc., has been a dumping yard for the powerful states and a laboratory to test their policies. Ukrainians, as well as the Russian population and, with it, the whole of Eastern Europe, as it has been caught at the crossroads of European–Western and Russian power politics since 24, February 2022, have suffered tremendously. No excitement about the invasion of Russia over Ukraine has been described as *Zeitenwende*, “a historical turning point with multi-polar world order now a reality” (Flochkart & Korosteleva, 2022, p. 466) and “an epochal tectonic shift” (Laruelle, 2022, p. 9). While US and NATO support for the war has been continuous and enormous, it has not been honest with its so-called friends to like-minded democracies' principles (Heuvel, 2022). Instead, the US has been blamed as the primary cause of the fractures in the post-USSR Eastern Europe security environment and the originator of the crisis in the European balance of power. From a third-world perspective, Ukraine has turned into a battleground both literally and metaphorically as the competition for power and influence grows among the major players of the international system.

As we argued earlier, Putin, with his ongoing invasion of Ukraine, can be held as the original violator of international law as there is no legal or moral justification for invading a sovereign territorial entity known as a nation-state in the post-Westphalia era. With sophisticated reasoning, the paper also clarified that the US cannot hide its part of the blame for factoring as an important cause of the continuing crisis and the

responsibility for the contemporary war. The tussle for gaining preponderance over the Ukrainian State, added to the US and European Union hobnobbing with the Kyiv government against continuous Russian warnings, gives Ukraine a very hard time navigating its foreign policy choices. On the other hand, the skillful Russian framing of the conflict and its control over some already important territories of Ukraine give Ukraine few chances to maneuver the hard power and the sharp power directed at it.

Russian geopolitics, popularized and represented as Eurasianism by Alexander Dugin, believes that it should, by nature, have a greater influence in its near abroad than the West (Wolff, 2015), also known as Russia's "sphere of privileged interests" (McFaul et al., 2014, p. 168). This logic portends the neo-imperialistic thinking of Russia and its elite policy makers who aspire to dictate the economic and foreign policies in its neighborhood. This line of thinking is no different from the Monroe doctrine of the US, "which declares that Washington will oppose political and military incursions into the western hemisphere by powers outside of it" (Long & Schulz, 2023). Both the states mock the international law and respect for the sovereignty of smaller states at the face of it. However, knowing the exact intensity or mathematical measurement of who does more is irrelevant. Policies and behavior like this of these two states, searching for "spheres of influence and dictating other countries' policies" (Heuvel, 2022), have not given Ukraine an independent agency to control its own politics and foreign relations in the international system. Typical similarities are shared between a civilizational state and a neo-imperialistic state; both try to control the territories and populations of the adjacent states using a mixture of hard, soft and sharp power techniques.

The Civilizational façade has worked as a handy weapon in the hands of Moscow leadership to legitimize its ostensible civilizational project. Putin, whom Kissinger regarded as "a serious strategist — on the premises of Russian history" (Kissinger, 2014b, p. 2), nevertheless is adamant that he must bring his nation's imperial past back to its former glory of the Soviet era. Scholars who have studied Putin and Kremlinologists alike consider empire-building as the only true motive of Moscow (Braun, 2014, p. 34-42; Gressel, 2015, p. 2-3; Socor, 2016, p. 187-192). Putin invaded Ukraine as Brzezinski points out "without Ukraine, Russia ceases to be an empire" (Saradzhyan 2014). "Putin wanted Ukraine as part of a reconstituted Russian Empire; he also feared a democratic, modern, and prosperous Ukraine as an alternative model for Russians next door. He

will not get the former but may believe he can prevent the latter” (Taylor & Frantz 2023, p. 8).

While the war has seen a positive influence of Putin among the Russian population within Russia and a rise in his popularity, in Ukraine, it has gone down. According to the Levada Center, Putin's ratings have improved, with more than 80% of Russians surveyed supporting his military action (Yuri Levada Analytical Center, 2022). Similarly, according to a survey conducted by the Kyiv International Sociology Institute (KMIS) in the aftermath of the war over Crimea, the positive attitudes toward Russia among Ukrainians fell from 80% to 48% (Kirichenko, 2014). In these war phases, while on the one hand, Kyiv has gone closer to Washington, on the other, it has given Ukrainian nationalism a new life. Having poisoned Ukrainian-Russian relations for decades, Moscow has also contributed to national consolidation in Ukraine, albeit on an anti-Russian basis. At the same time, this consolidation is also largely pro-Western and supports the long-term trend of growing pro-European aspirations in Ukrainian society. This new pro-European consensus is reflected in the outcome of the early parliamentary elections in October 2014: both the Communists and the far right failed to enter the parliament, and the Party of Regions is now in the opposition, while pro-European and pro-Ukrainian democratic forces won the overwhelming majority of the seats.

Many important studies have shown that in Ukrainian society, many people view nationalism as a tool of de-Sovietisation that is warranted by the neighboring country's external aggressiveness (Zhurzhenko, 2014, p. 249-267). The Kremlin and its ruling elite have significantly contributed to Ukraine's national cohesion by offering the ideal representation of an external adversary. This laid the foundation for constructing a civic Ukrainian nation, and the events since 2022 have solidified the resolve of both the leadership and the people to build a modern political nation. Events like the Maidan protests and the wars for overturning the forceful Russian integration of Kyiv which means creating a new political nation with a modern civil society unified by a collective history have become the substantive features of an emerging nascent project of Ukrainian nationhood. As a rebuttal to Putin's 2020 declaration that “Russia is not just a country. It is really a separate civilization” (The Moscow Times, 2020), “most Ukrainians want no part of Putin’s vicious concept of a separate civilization—especially now that his military is killing men,

women, and children indiscriminately” (Hirsh, 2022, p. 10) This new phase of national awakening and consolidating a pan-Ukrainian national identity gives Ukraine a chance and a solid reason to shape its destinies according to its wishes without any coercion from above by any powerful state but only after the war phase is over.

Conclusion and Way Forward

As B. Russett and M. Cox, in a brilliant article "Clash of Civilizations, or Realism and Liberalism Deja Vu? Some Evidence," claim that Huntington bringing civilizational understanding upfront at the international level in the contemporary international relations literature deserves appreciation, although this framework does not successfully explain the major crisis at the international level (Russett et al., 2000, p. 583–608). No single theory or framework has all the answers to our problems, yet they contain valuable insights about the very problems that we confront. The holistic civilizational understanding of conflicts at much deeper levels from the scholars and foreign policy pundits, which will lay bare the motivation of the leaders for any confrontation, needs to be improved. Understanding a civilizational perspective, which leaders often have invoked to legitimize their aggressive political standing, hence deserves a well-grounded engagement, which has unfortunately not been the case. The literature reviewed for the paper found very few standard studies linking Civilizational motivation behind the global crisis, particularly in the context of Ukraine. This deficiency (gap) in research can be highlighted by looking at the reputed Foreign Affairs Journal's take on Ukraine. Although various aspects of the present war and Ukraine crisis have been analyzed extraordinarily and in length, not a single article from Nov. 21 November 2019, to 18 January 2024, directly relating the Civilizational aspect with the conflict or the civilizational motivation of the Russian leadership (whether as a façade or real) behind the conflict, has found space within the plethora of its pages. Charles Kupchan's invocation of analyzing the conflict in the geopolitical as well as civilizational dimension makes sense then (Kupchan, 2019, p. 3-9).

The complete escalation of the crisis and a viable solution for the whole conflict cannot be postponed for the future as it is “a defining factor for the future European security” (Giles et al., 2015, p. vi) and is rightly considered the biggest danger to the European system in more than five decades. For John Morrison, the Russian-Ukrainian relationship is to

Eastern Europe, and the Franco-German relationship is to Western Europe. Just as the latter provides the core of the European Union, the former is the core essential to unity in the Orthodox world (Morrison, 1993, p. 677-703). No side will be ready to compromise regarding securing their security against the entity they regarded as an enemy. Therefore, the present course of action would lie in keeping the crisis under check instead of escalating it beyond the controllable levels till a permanent ceasefire and serious measures to overhaul the security matters are dealt with honestly without basing the decisions on zero-sum gains. The way forward and plans to be implemented are already outlined in lengthy details by scholars; however, what is required is an honest and humanistic approach by the leadership of the powerful states to solve the crisis. One way forward can be asking for help from the "Habermasian notion of some base universal truths that exist in the context-free environment, and thus are verifiable across different cultural settings" (Chebankova, 2021, p. 28). This approach will provide a framework to look at the problem from the other side's vantage point without locking the horns and engage with different perspectives without trying to control the critical discourse at play from each side. From an ethical-normative position, it means giving equal weight to all civilizations and considering other civilizations as knowledge hubs and cradles of learning without being oblivious to the universality of barbarism and savagery within them. The engagement around a synchronic approach within civilizations and modern nation-states would provide a critical backgrounder while conducting a harmonious international political dialogue to solve the wider European security crisis.

References

- Appiah, K. A. (2017, November 28). There is no such thing as western civilisation. *The Guardian*. <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2016/nov/09/western-civilisation-appiah-reith-lecture>
- Aroua, A. (2006). *The clash of civilizations: A conflictology perspective* (p. 1). Centre for Conflict and Peace Studies—Cordoba Foundation of Geneva. https://www.academia.edu/77974016/The_Clash_of_Civilizations_A_Conflictology_Perspective

- Assumpção, C. (2020, January 29). Is Huntington's clash of civilizations a self-fulfilled prophecy? *E-International Relations*. https://www.e-ir.info/2020/01/29/is-huntingtons-clash-of-civilizations-a-self-fulfilled-prophecy/#google_vignette
- Barkanov, B. (2015). Crisis in Ukraine: Clash of civilizations or geopolitics? In R. E. Kanet & M. Sussex (Eds.), *Power, politics and confrontation in Eurasia: Foreign policy in a contested region* (p. 211). Palgrave Macmillan UK.
- Bergmann, M., Dolbaia, T., & Fenton, N. (2022, December 14). Russia's adaptation game: Deciphering the Kremlin's "humanitarian policy". *Center for Strategic and International Studies (CSIS)*. <https://www.csis.org/analysis/russias-adaptation-game-deciphering-kremlins-humanitarian-policy>
- Bohomolov, O., & Lytvynenko, O. V. (2012). *A ghost in the mirror: Russian soft power in Ukraine* (p. 3). Chatham House.
- Braudel, F., & Mayne, R. (1995). *A history of civilizations*. Penguin Books.
- Braun, A. (2014). Tougher sanctions now: Putin's delusional quest for empire. *World Affairs*, 177(2), 34–42.
- Chebankova, E. (2021). What is civilization? Problems and definitions. In E. Chebankova & P. Dutkiewicz (Eds.), *Civilizations and world order* (pp. 19–33). Routledge.
- Chebankova, E., & Dutkiewicz, P. (Eds.). (2021). *Civilizations and world order* (p. 159). Routledge.
- Coker, C. (2019). *The rise of the civilizational state* (p. 11). John Wiley & Sons.
- Cotter, B. P. (2016). Russkiy Mir: How the Kremlin employs narratives to destabilize the Baltic States. *George C. Marshall Center for European Studies*. https://www.marshallcenter.org/sites/default/files/files/2020-09/pC_v7%20Special%20Edition_en-6_Cotter.pdf
- D'Anieri, P. (2019). *Ukraine and Russia: From civilized divorce to uncivil war* (p. i). Cambridge University Press.
- Dugin, A. (2012). *The fourth political theory*. Arktos.
- Evans, P. (1997). The clash of civilizations and the remaking of the world order [Review of the book *The Clash of Civilizations and the Remaking of World Order*, by S. P. Huntington]. *Contemporary Sociology*, 26(6), 691. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2654621>
- Flockhart, T., & Korosteleva, E. A. (2022). War in Ukraine: Putin and the multi-order world. *Contemporary Security Policy*, 43(3), 466. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13523260.2022.2091591>

- Fukuyama, F. (1996, November 7). Still a dangerous place. *The Wall Street Journal*. <https://www.wsj.com/articles/SB847319278492373500>
- Giles, K., Hanson, P., Lyne, R., Nixey, J., Sherr, J., & Wood, A. (2015). *The Russian challenge* (p. vi). Chatham House. https://www.chathamhouse.org/sites/files/chathamhouse/field/field_document/20150605RussianChallengeGilesHansonLyneNixeySherrWood.pdf
- Gioe, D. V., & Styles, W. (2022). Vladimir Putin's Russian world turned upside down. *Armed Forces & Society*, 49(4), 598–614. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1177/0095327X221121778>
- Götz, E., & Staun, J. (2022). Why Russia attacked Ukraine: Strategic culture and radicalized narratives. *Contemporary Security Policy*, 43(3), 482–497. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13523260.2022.2082633>
- Gressel, G. (2015). *Russia's quiet military revolution, and what it means for Europe* (pp. 2–3). European Council on Foreign Relations. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/pdf/resrep21638.pdf>
- Haynes, J. (2021). From Huntington to Trump: Twenty-five years of the “Clash of Civilizations”. *The Review of Faith & International Affairs*, 17(1), 11–23. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15570274.2019.1570755>
- Heuvel, K. (2022, February 15). A path out of the Ukraine crisis. *The Washington Post*. <https://www.washingtonpost.com/opinions/2022/02/15/path-out-of-ukraine-crisis/>
- Hirsh, M. (2022, April 10). The month that changed a century. *Foreign Policy*. <https://foreignpolicy.com/2022/04/10/russia-ukraine-war-postwar-global-order-civilization/>
- Hovorun, C. (2016). Interpreting the “Russian world.” In A. Krawchuk & T. Bremer (Eds.), *Churches in the Ukrainian crisis* (p. 163). Palgrave Macmillan. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-34144-6_8
- Huntington, S. P. (1996). *The clash of civilizations and the remaking of world order*. Simon & Schuster.
- Huntington, S. P. (1996a). *The clash of civilizations* (p. 37). Simon & Schuster.
- Huntington, S. P. (2004b). *Who are we?: The challenges to America's national identity* (p. 405). Simon & Schuster.
- Jennings, J. (2016). *Killing civilization: A reassessment of early urbanism and its consequences* (p. 7). University of New Mexico Press.
- Jung, C. G. (1959). *The archetypes and the collective unconscious*. Pantheon.

- Katzenstein, P. J. (2010). "Walls" between "those people"? Contrasting perspectives on world politics. *Perspectives on Politics*, 8(1), 11–25. <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/perspectives-on-politics/article/walls-between-those-people-contrasting-perspectives-on-world-politics/8C7CFE7259EC110EA9004947E526FF4B>
- Kendall-Taylor, A., & Frantz, E. (2023). The treacherous path to a better Russia: Ukraine's future and Putin's fate. *Foreign Affairs*, 102(8). <https://www.foreignaffairs.com/russian-federation/treacherous-path-better-russia>
- Kirichenko, I. (2014, February 9). Interview with Vladimir Paniotto. *Ukraina-Rossia: Nervnaia liubov', neravnaia nenavist'*. *Zerkalo Nedeli*. <http://gazeta.zn.ua/internal/ukraina-rossiya-nervnaya-lyubov-neravnaya-nenavist-.html>
- Kissinger, H. (2014). *World order*. Penguin.
- Kissinger, H. (2014a, March 5). How the Ukraine crisis ends. *The Washington Post*. https://www.washingtonpost.com/opinions/henry-kissinger-to-settle-the-ukraine-crisis-start-at-the-end/2014/03/05/46dad868-a496-11e3-8466-d34c451760b9_story.html
- Kupchan, C. A. (2019). On great power conflict. *Strategic Studies Quarterly*, 13(4), 3–9. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/26815042>
- Laruelle, M. (2022). Putin's war and the dangers of Russian disintegration. *Foreign Affairs*. <https://www.foreignaffairs.com/russian-federation/putins-war-and-dangers-russian-disintegration>
- Lewicki, G. G. (2023). Civilizational security: Why the Russian invasion of Ukraine shows that 'national security' is not enough to understand geopolitics. *Comparative Civilizations Review*, 89(89), Article 11. <https://scholarsarchive.byu.edu/ccr/vol89/iss89/11/>
- McFaul, M., Sestanovich, S., & Mearsheimer, J. J. (2014). Faulty powers: Who started the Ukraine crisis? *Foreign Affairs*, 93(6), 167–178. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/24483933>
- McTague, T. (2022, February 9). Vladimir Putin is a product of modernity: Why the tension in Ukraine may feel deceptively regressive. *The Atlantic*. <https://www.theatlantic.com/international/archive/2022/02/russia-invade-ukraine-putin-strategy/621626/>
- Mearsheimer, J. J. (2022). The causes and consequences of the Ukraine war. *Horizons: Journal of International Relations and Sustainable Development*, (21), 12-27. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/48686693>

- Merry E. W. (2016). The Origins of Russia's War in Ukraine: The Clash of Russian and European "Civilizational Choices" for Ukraine. In Elizabeth A. Wood, William E. Pomerantz, W W Merry and Maxim Trudolyubov, *Roots of Russia's War in Ukraine* (pp. 27). (Columbia University Press).
- Morrison J. (1993). Pereyaslav and after: the Russian—Ukrainian relationship. *International Affairs*, 69(4), 677-703. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2620592>
- Pieper M. (2020). Russkiy mir: the geopolitics of Russian compatriots abroad. *Geopolitics*, 25(3), 756-779. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14650045.2018.1465047>
- Rubenstein R. E., & Crocker J. (1994). Challenging Huntington. *Foreign Policy*, (96), 113-128. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/1149220>
- Russett B. M., Oneal J. R., & Cox M. (2000). Clash of civilizations, or realism and liberalism déjà vu? Some evidence. *Journal of Peace Research*, 37(5), 583-608. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022343300037005003>
- Saradzhyan S. (2014, 25 February). *Does Russia Need Ukraine?* The National Interest. <https://www.belfercenter.org/publication/does-russia-really-need-ukraine>.
- Schulz Long. (2023, 16 December). The Return of the Monroe Doctrine. *Foreign Policy*. <https://foreignpolicy.com/2023/12/16/monroe-doctrine-united-states-latin-america-foreign-policy-interventionism-china-gop/>.
- Sharif R., Hanif K., Iftikhar A., et al. (2023). Russia–Ukraine Conflict: Clash of Interest not a Clash of Civilization. *CEMJP*, 31(4), 440-446. http://journals.kozminski.cemj.org/index.php/pl_cemj/article/view/1110
- Socor V. (2016). Conserved Conflict: Russia's Pattern in Ukraine's East. In N. Iancu, A. Fortuna, C. Barna (Eds.), *Countering Hybrid Threats: Lessons Learned from Ukraine* (pp. 187-192). IOS Press.
- Spengler, O. (1926). *The decline of the West* (C. F. Atkinson, Trans.). Alfred A. Knopf. (Original work published 1918).
- Terlouw, K. P., & Lewicki, G. G. (2016). Trading identities: Neomedievalism and the urban future. In G. G. Lewicki (Ed.), *Cities in the neomedieval era* (pp. 45–64). IMPART.
- The Moscow Times. (2020, 18 May). *Russia Is a 'Distinct Civilization,' Putin Says*. <https://www.themoscowtimes.com/2020/05/18/russia-is-a-distinct-civilization-putin-says-a70295>.

- Toynbee, A. (1946). *A study of history*. Oxford University Press.
- Wallerstein, I. (1992). *Geopolitics and geoculture: Essays on the changing world-system*. Cambridge University Press.
- Weller P. (2010). The clash of civilisations thesis and religious responses. *European Journal of Economic and Political Studies*, 3(1), 83. <https://repository.derby.ac.uk/item/942v1/the-clash-of-civilisations-thesis-and-religious-responses>
- Wolff A. T. (2015). The future of NATO enlargement after the Ukraine crisis. *International Affairs*, 91(5), 1103-1121. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-2346.12400>
- Young B. R. (2022). Putin has a grimly absolute vision of the 'Russian World'. *Foreign Policy*, 6(03). <https://www.almendron.com/tribuna/putin-has-a-grimly-absolute-vision-of-the-russian-world/>
- Yuri Levada Analytical Center. (2022, 11 November). The Conflict With Ukraine. *Levada-Center*. <https://www.levada.ru/en/2022/04/11/the-conflict-with-ukraine/>
- Zhurzhenko T. (2014). A divided nation? Reconsidering the role of identity politics in the Ukraine crisis. *Die Friedens-Warte*, 89(1/2)249-267. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/24868495>